

Research Article

In silico Designed Aptamer for the Detection of Bacteria Leaf Blight Disease in Paddy by Targeting the Virulence Protein

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Abstract: Bacteria Panicle Blight (BPB) is a newly emerging disease of paddy caused by *Burkholderia glumae*. Its devastating effect to paddy is owed to the pathogenicity of toxoflavin that is produced by the bacterium through the assistance of sequential protein expression event. Usually, the detection is made by manual observation or sending them to the laboratory for testing. These methods are quite laborious and time consuming for immediate action. Usually, real time sensors require antibody for the disease detection which may be costly and produce inconsistent results. In this study, aptamers were used as capturing agent in place of traditional antibody method. Also, the selected aptamers were innovatively designed in silico, unlike the conventional SELEX method that is costly, laborious and time consuming. After screening 33 aptamers through molecular docking, 4 were objected to molecular dynamics simulation and MM-PBSA to predict binding properties. Through computational results, the aptamer candidates exhibited lowest docking energy and best interaction when simulated at 200nanoseconds and when tested experimentally, they give high affinity towards target protein. This innovation may cut short the time needed to develop drugs and sensing agents since it can save millions in terms of research budget and development costs. This innovation also has high commercialization potential as the only material it needs is a high end computer which is comparatively cheaper than many research equipment required in other methods.

Keywords: aptamer; in-silico; Molecular Dynamics.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In silico designed aptamers have emerged as a promising tool in the field of biosensors, offering enhanced sensitivity and specificity for various applications. These synthetic oligonucleotides, generated through computational modeling software, have been successfully integrated into a range of biosensor platforms such as electrochemical sensors and Lateral Flow Assays. One of the significant applications of *in silico* designed aptamers is in the detection of pathogenic bacteria. Aptamers targeting bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* (Roper-Vega et al., 2022) have been successfully developed through computational techniques. These aptamers were incorporated into electrochemical biosensors, lateral flow assays etc achieving high sensitivity and specificity in identifying bacterial presence in food

samples of up to 27 CFU/ml. This advancement is crucial for food safety, enabling rapid detection of contaminants that can lead to foodborne illnesses.

In silico designed aptamers through computational design process significantly reduces the time and cost associated with traditional aptamer selection methods especially in biosensors development. This is because *in silico* modeling allows for the prediction of high-affinity aptamers tailored to specific targets, enhancing the specificity of the biosensors. In addition, in the AI era, the development of drug and capture agents such as aptamers that are facilitated by computers can expedite the process and therefore will save more time while being cost effective, making it aligned with Industrial Revolution 4.0.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The methods require online and offline software such as mfold, RNA Composer, hdock, Autodock Vina, Charmm, Gromacs and MMPBSA. The candidates for docking were first folded with mfold and converted to pdb file with RNA Composer. The target protein and the aptamer were then docked with hdock and Autodock Vina. The resulting docked complex were subjected force field energy application to prepare it for docking. Next, they were subjected to molecular dynamics calculation and simulation using Gromacs and MM-PBSA at 200nanoseconds. The good values screened were below-100 kcal/mole for free binding energy delta G. Next, the aptamers were tested for sensing ability using Screen Printed Gold Electrode (SPGE).

Figure 1. The flow for the *in silico* design of aptamer.

Figure 2. The flow for the Screen Printed Gold Electrode sensor to test the feasibility of the designed aptamer.

3. FINDINGS

3.2.1 Docking and Molecular Simulation

The best two candidates were chosen for further sensor development which are Bg11A and HgtRNA7. Initially, the docking score for the 2 candidates were -7 kcal/mol and below. After subjecting them to Molecular Dynamics with Gromacs, the values given were between -100kcal/mol to -130kcal.mol. The findings were as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. This is the result obtained from hdock and Autodock Vina through rigid docking.

APTAMER NAME	DOCKING SCORE (HDOCK)	LIGAND RMSD (Å) (HDOCK)	CONFIDENCE SCORE	INTERFACE RESIDUES (PAIR)	BINDING AFFINITY (KCAL/MOL) (AUTODOCK VINA, GROMACS)
BG11A	-307.74	N/A	0.9591	14	-17.7; -130
HGTRNA7	-355.17	48.26	0.9838	23	-16; 120

Figure 3. This is the detection obtained electrochemically where the presence of the candidate protein ToxA is exhibited by peak shift away from B PBS and Bare.

3.2.2 Development of Sensor through electrochemistry

The designed aptamers were immobilized onto SPGE to develop a sensor. The sensors fabricated were read with chronoamperometric method of Cyclic Voltammetry. From figure 3, readings from electrochemistry exhibits the presence of the candidate protein when spiked on the SPGE where it can be detected to up 10^{-10} M.

4. DISCUSSION

For a capture agent to be practical and usable, it is important to determine a strong binding affinity towards the target. Very low numbers predicted through computer simulations and molecular modelling have assisted in tight binding capture agent-target complex. We have observed that binding energy provided by molecular dynamics of lesser than -100 kcal/mole can give a tight binding therefore can be immobilized on sensors to detect its candidate. This is because the more negative the numbers, the more spontaneous the reaction.

5. CONCLUSION

In silico designed aptamers represent a significant advancement in biosensor technology, with successful applications across various domains, including food safety, environmental monitoring, and medical diagnostics. Our techniques produced comparable results to many other aptamers designed from the laborious SELEX experiment i.e. Alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) aptamer AP273 which may take about 6 months to complete. They adopt computational modelling and Molecular Dynamics to help enhance the binding of drug towards the target (Zhang et al., 2023). Meanwhile, our group designed it from scratch which exempts the need to perform SELEX in order to design an aptamer.

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